

HASIL BELAJAR MAHASISWA: ANALISIS BUTIR SOAL TES

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk menguji validitas, reliabilitas, indeks kesukaran, dan daya beda soal tes untuk mahasiswa. Populasi penelitian adalah mahasiswa jurusan Teknik Otomotif UNP sebanyak 28 orang. Sampel penelitian dipilih dengan teknik *total sampling* sehingga keseluruhan populasi menjadi sampel penelitian. Teknik pengumpulan data dilakukan dengan dokumentasi yaitu berupa pemberian dan pengumpulan soal tes; kunci jawaban; dan lembar jawaban soal tes. Analisis data menggunakan teknik analisis deskriptif kuantitatif. Hasil analisis data menghasilkan tingkat validitas, reliabilitas, indeks kesukaran, dan daya beda soal tes. Hasil analisis data yaitu soal tes kategori valid, indeks reliabilitas soal pada kriteria reliabilitas tinggi, indeks kesukaran dengan kategori butir soal baik/layak, dan daya pembeda butir soal termasuk klasifikasi soal yang baik. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, maka disimpulkan bahwa soal tes yang diberikan kepada mahasiswa layak untuk digunakan sebagai salah satu tes untuk mengukur kemampuan kognitif mahasiswa.

Kata Kunci: analisis butir; soal tes; kategori soal tes.

Abstract

The purpose of the research was to see the level of validity, reliability, index of difficulty, and differentiating power of student test questions. The research population were 28 students majoring in Automotive Engineering of UNP. The research sample was selected using a total sampling technique, so that the entire population became the research sample. Data collection techniques used documentation in the form of giving and collecting test questions; answer key; and the answer sheet for the test. Data analysis used quantitative descriptive analysis techniques. The results of data analysis will produce levels of validity, reliability, index of difficulty, and differentiating power of test questions. The results of the data analysis concluded that the test items were in the valid category, the reliability index of the questions on the criteria of high reliability, the difficulty index with the category of good/decent items, and the discriminating power of the items including the good classification of questions. Based on the results of the research, it was concluded that the test questions given to students deserved to be used as a test to measure students' cognitive abilities.

Keywords: item analysis; test questions; test question category.